

The Modified Gait Efficacy Scale: A cross-cultural adaptation for use with the Hindi-speaking Population in India

Paulraj Manickavelu ^{1,*}, Ritisha Namballa ¹, Anand Babu Kaliyaperumal ¹, Simulia Dhinju Benjamin ²

¹ Sri Venkateshwaraa College of Physiotherapy, Sri Venkateshwaraa College of Paramedical Sciences, Affiliated with Pondicherry University, Ariyur, Puducherry, India.

² Jijamata College of Physiotherapy, Majalgaon, Maharashtra, India.

*. **Corresponding author:** Paulraj Manickavelu, Sri Venkateshwaraa College of Physiotherapy, Sri Venkateshwaraa College of Paramedical Sciences, Affiliated with Pondicherry University, Ariyur, Puducherry, India. Phone: 00997878 04626. Email: mrajpaul@gmail.com.

Cite this article: Manickavelu, P., Namballa, R., Kaliyaperumal, A.B., Benjamin, S.D. The Modified Gait Efficacy Scale: A cross-cultural adaptation for use with the Hindi-speaking Population in India. Int J Epidemiol Health Sci 2024;5: e79. Doi: [10.51757/IJEHS.5.2024.717653](https://doi.org/10.51757/IJEHS.5.2024.717653).

Abstract

Background: Mobility refers to the ability to move between different community situations, such as one's own home, the surrounding neighborhood, and beyond. The rate of deterioration in walking speed and other indications of lower limb function frequently accelerates throughout the seventh decade of life. The m-GES is a 10-item questionnaire intended primarily to assess activities encountered during routine walking in daily life. However, a number of cultural and language hurdles prevent MGES from being widely used in India. The goal of this project is to culturally adapt and translate the Modified Gait Efficacy Scale (MGES) for the Hindi-speaking community in India.

Methodology: This paper is a translation of the American Academy of Orthopedic Surgeons' 2007 guidelines. The cross-cultural adaption process was divided into many steps, including gaining consent from the tool developer, forward translation, forward translation synthesis, back translations, back translation synthesis, and pretesting.

Results: The English version of the MGES showed strong internal consistency, with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.93. Preliminary results indicate that the adapted scale is culturally suitable and relevant to Hindi-speaking older individuals.

Conclusion: The current era of evidence-based clinical practice emphasizes the need of using proper intervention approaches to address issues related to competent clinical reasoning by physicians using suitable diagnostic tools. Thus, the Hindi version of MGES was generated by changing the original English version using a cross-cultural adaptation procedure.

Keywords: Gait efficacy, Self-efficacy, Hindi Culture, Translation, Falls Prevention, Geriatrics, India

Introduction

Mobility is essential for active ageing, which is linked to health and quality of life. Mobility, defined as the ability to move across community environments—from one's home to the neighborhood and beyond—becomes more vital as people age. According to research,

walking speed and other measures of lower extremity function tend to diminish over time, particularly after the seventh decade (1). According to the Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation (MoSPI)'s 'Elderly in India-2021' study, the proportion of older individuals aged 60 and over has increased from 8.6%

in 2011 to 10.1% in 2021, with forecasts indicating that it will grow to 13.1% by 2031 (2).

Age-related movement decrease is a universal biological process influenced by a variety of organ systems, including the central nervous system, perceptual system, peripheral neural system, muscles, bones, joints, and energy metabolism (3). Walking ability can be hampered by malfunction in these systems, such as those caused by a stroke or hip fracture, or by a general increase in frailty (4).

Several diagnostic methods are used to examine older individuals' mobility and balance, including the Timed Up and Go (TUG) test (5), the Short Physical Performance Battery (SPPB) (6), the Dynamic Gait Index (DGI) (7), and the Berg Balance Scale (BBS) (8). These tools differ in their approach: some focus on qualitative features, while others include quantitative measurements. For example, the TUG test quantifies mobility by measuring the time it takes to get out of a chair, walk three meters, turn, walk back, and sit down (5). In contrast, the Berg Balance Scale assesses balance through a series of exercises that evaluate both static and dynamic balance (8).

The Gait Efficacy Scale (GES) was originally designed to assess a person's confidence in their ability to walk. The m-GES is a modified version that is intended to better reflect daily walking experiences. Various task teams of the American Physical Therapy Association's Neurology Section have endorsed the GES for use in illnesses such as Multiple Sclerosis, Parkinson's disease, spinal cord injury, stroke, traumatic brain injury, and vestibular disorders (9).

In India, which has tremendous linguistic diversity—28 states and 8 union territories, each with its own regional language—the use of the GES is limited due to the supremacy of English in its original form. Hindi, the world's third most spoken language and a key language on the Indian subcontinent, offers a feasible alternative for greater accessibility (10). Given its broad reach and cultural relevance, translating the GES into Hindi would allow for better application in the Indian context. The process of "cross-cultural adaptation" includes both linguistic translation and cultural changes to ensure that the instrument is relevant and understandable to the target community (11-13).

The purpose of this study is to cross-culturally adapt and translate the MGES into Hindi for use by Hindi-speaking older persons in community settings. This adaptation procedure is critical for ensuring the tool's effectiveness and accuracy in assessing gait efficacy in this particular demographic.

Methods

This cross-sectional study investigates the Modified Gait Efficacy Scale (MGES)'s cross-cultural adaptation for older persons who speak Hindi. It is important to note that the study did not assess the reliability and validity of the translated version of the scale. The major goal is to culturally and linguistically modify the scale for usage with Hindi-speaking older people.

Purposive sampling was used to identify participants who matched certain inclusion criteria: community-dwelling older people aged 60 and over, who could speak Hindi and English and could walk independently or with minimum help. The sample included 150 people from Jharkhand. This strategy ensured that the sample was representative of the target demographic to which the MGES-H was being tailored. Individuals with neurological illnesses (e.g., Parkinson's disease, dementia), orthopedic concerns (e.g., fractures, osteoporosis), cardiovascular conditions, or uncontrolled hypertension were excluded to prevent confounding factors that could affect mobility assessments (14).

Description of Tool

The Modified Gait Efficacy Scale (mGES) is a frequently used tool for measuring elderly people's confidence in executing walking tasks. The mGES is a 10-item questionnaire with a 10-point Likert scale and a score range of 10 to 100. The scale's original objective is to assess people's confidence in their walking abilities, but this study focuses on modifying the scale for cultural and linguistic relevance in the Hindi-speaking community (15).

Table 1. Modified Items

Item No	Original Item	Modified Item
1	Safely walk on a level surface such as hardwood floor	Safely walk on a level surface such as a concrete floor
4	Safely step down from a curb	Safely step down from an edge
5	Safely step up onto a curb	Safely step up onto an edge

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics of Participants by Gender, Education, Comorbidities, Fall History, and Assistive Device Use

Category	Subcategory	Frequency	Percentage	Mean (years)	Age	Std. Dev.	Age Range
Gender	Male			65.34		5.30	60-83
	Female			64.76		4.90	60-83
Education	School	4	2.6				
	High School	58	38.7				
	Graduate	88	58.7				
Comorbidities	Diabetes	34	22.7				
	Diabetes & Hypertension	4	2.7				
	Hypertension	26	17.3				
	None	86	57.3				
Fall History	Yes	4	2.7				
	None	146	97.3				
Assistive Devices	Stick	3	2.0				
	Walker	2	1.3				
	None	145	96.7				

Procedure

The adaptation process for the MGES-H involved several phases:

Phase 1: Adaptation Process

The adaptation used cross-cultural adaptation approaches to ensure cultural relevance for Hindi-speaking people. Seven of the initial ten items on the mGES remained unchanged. Three elements were culturally modified, as shown in Table 1. The changes were designed to assure semantic, experiential, and conceptual similarity among the Hindi-speaking Indian people. The term "hardwood floor" was substituted with "concrete floor" as "pakkee evam samatal satah", and the term "curb" was replaced with "edge" as "kinaare". These revisions were accepted by Dr. Jennifer S. Brach, the MGES creator.

Phase 2: Forward Translation Process

Two multilingual translators, both native Hindi speakers, translated the updated MGES from English to Hindi, resulting in two separate versions. An independent translator then compared the texts and created a composite version to fix any inconsistencies (16).

Phase 3: Backward Translation Process

Two bilingual translators, one specializing in botany and the other in quality assurance, translated the MGES-H back into English. An independent physiotherapy professor analyzed and integrated these translations to create a single back-translation. A Chief Medical Superintendent reviewed the backward-translated pre-final MGES-H and modified MGES-E versions and found that they were identical in formatting and language (17).

Reliability and Validity

The original Modified Gait Efficacy Scale (MGES) had a good level of internal consistency in English, with a Cronbach's alpha score of 0.93, indicating trustworthy performance in the English-speaking population (15). This study did not test the MGES-H's reliability or validity. The emphasis was exclusively on the cross-cultural adaptation and translation processes. Future research is required to assess the reliability and validity of the MGES-H.

Expert Committee

The modification process was overseen by an expert group that includes psychologists, exercise

physiologists, senior physiotherapists, student researchers, and a Hindi language expert. The participation of a Hindi language expert guaranteed that the revised MGES-H appropriately reflected the Hindi language's cultural and linguistic characteristics (18).

Results

Demographic Analysis

The study included 150 individuals, with 109 men (72.7%) and 41 women (27.3%). The participants' mean age was 65.18 ± 5.24 years, with a range of 60 to 83 years. The average age and standard deviation for each gender are also provided (Table 2).

Educational Status and Comorbidities

Among the participants, 88 (58.7%) were graduates, 58 (38.7%) had completed high school, and 4 (2.7%) had only finished school (Table 2). In terms of comorbidities, 34 patients (22.7%) had diabetes, 4 (2.7%) had both diabetes and hypertension, 26 (17.3%) had hypertension, and 86 (57.3%) had no comorbidities.

Fall History and Use of Assistive Devices

Four (2.7%) of the 150 individuals reported a history of falls (Table 2). Three individuals (2.0%) used a stick, two (1.3%) used a walker, and 145 (96.7%) did not use any assistance aids.

Flowchart of Adaptation Process

The phases of the adaptation process are:

1. **Phase 1:** Adaptation Process
 - Initial modifications and cultural adjustments of MGES.
2. **Phase 2:** Forward Translation Process
 - Translation of the adapted MGES into Hindi.
3. **Phase 3:** Backward Translation Process
 - Back-translation into English and comparison with the original version.
4. **Phase 4 and 5:** Not included in this study.

Discussion

This study examined the Modified Gait Efficacy Scale (mGES)'s cross-cultural adaptation for Hindi-speaking older individuals. The adaptation process included changing elements for cultural significance and translating the scale into Hindi. The study did not involve psychometric testing, such as reliability and

validity assessments, which are required for future reviews.

The mGES's therapeutic value has resulted in its adaptation and validation in a variety of languages and geographies. For example, the Turkish version of the MGES (T-MGES) has been validated for its relationship to the Activities-specific Balance Confidence Scale (ABC) and the Falls Efficacy Scale-International (FES-I). Factor analysis indicated that T-MGES is a simple, one-dimensional measure of walking confidence in older individuals who live in the community (19). Similarly, the Dutch version of the MGES evaluated ceiling and floor impacts in a large cohort and found no significant concerns, which is consistent with the findings of the Turkish study (20). The Brazilian version of the MGES (MGES-Brazil) showed test-retest reliability and was validated in a clinical group of stroke survivors. This version demonstrated reliability in assessing changes in walking confidence in clinical settings (21). In contrast, our study focused on healthy older persons, emphasizing the importance of testing MGES-H in a variety of populations to understand its broader application.

The German version of MGES (MGES-G) verified its relationships with other mobility-related self-efficacy scales as well as performance-based measures like gait speed and the square step test. The study concluded that more research is needed to corroborate these findings in primary care and clinical settings (22). The Japanese version (J-MGES) was found to be reliable and valid, with connections to physical performance and life span assessment (LSA) measures (23). These studies highlight the importance of continual validation across contexts and people.

One of the study's strengths is the rigorous cross-cultural modification of the MGES, which ensures that the tool is culturally and linguistically acceptable for older persons who speak Hindi. However, the study's drawback is the absence of a psychometric analysis of the adapted scale. Without assessing the MGES-H's reliability and validity, its efficiency in measuring gait efficacy among Hindi-speaking older persons is unknown.

Conclusion

The translation of the MGES into Hindi is an important step toward increasing the accessibility of gait efficacy assessments for Hindi-speaking older individuals. Future studies should focus on confirming the MGES-H's psychometric qualities, such as reliability, validity, and responsiveness. Furthermore, research should investigate the MGES-H's applicability in a variety of

clinical and community contexts to assure its efficacy across diverse groups.

Acknowledgement

We would like to thank Dr. Jennifer S. Brach for her encouragement and permission, as well as the expert committee members for their invaluable contributions.

Conflict of Interest: None.

References

1. Manini, T.M., Clark, B.C. Dynapenia and aging: an update. *J Gerontol A Biol Sci Med Sci* 2012;67(1):28-40.
2. Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation, Government of India. Elderly in India, 2021. Available from: https://mospi.gov.in/sites/default/files/publication_reports/Elderly%20in%20India%202021.pdf.
3. Thompson, H.J., McCormick, W.C., Kagan, S.H. Traumatic brain injury in older adults: epidemiology, outcomes, and future implications. *J Am Geriatr Soc* 2006;54(10):1590-5.
4. Fried, L.P., Ferrucci, L., Darer, J., Williamson, J.D., Anderson, G. Untangling the concepts of disability, frailty, and comorbidity: implications for improved targeting and care. *J Gerontol A Biol Sci Med Sci* 2004;59(3):255-63.
5. Podsiadlo, D., Richardson, S.. The timed "Up & Go": a test of basic functional mobility for frail elderly persons. *J Am Geriatr Soc* 1991;39(2):142-8.
6. Guralnik, J.M., Simonsick, E.M., Ferrucci, L., Glynn, R.J., Berkman, L.F., Blazer, D.G., et al. A short physical performance battery assessing lower extremity function: association with self-reported disability and prediction of mortality and nursing home admission. *J Gerontol* 1994;49(2):M85-94.
7. Shumway-Cook, A., Brauer, S., Woollacott, M.H. Predicting the probability for falls in community-dwelling older adults using the Berg Balance Scale. *J Gerontol A Biol Sci Med Sci* 2000;80(9):896-903.
8. Berg, K., Wood-Dauphinee, S., Williams, J.I., Maki, B. Measuring balance in the elderly: preliminary development of an instrument. *Phys Ther Canada* 1989;41(6):304-311.

9. Weijer, R.H.A., Hoozemans, M.J.M., van Dieën, J.H., Pijnappels, M. Construct validity and reliability of the modified gait efficacy scale for older adults. *Disabil Rehabil* 2022;44(11):2464-2469.
10. Kumar, V. Language mixing in Indian Linguistic Landscape. *Int J Innov TESOL Appl Linguistics* 2024; 9(3):1-5. Available from: <https://www.ijital.org/images/issues/current-issues/IJITAL%20Vol%209-Issue-3/V9-I3-Paper-3%20by%20Dr.%20Vivek.pdf>.
11. Beaton, D.E., Bombardier, C., Guillemin, F., Ferraz, M.B. Guidelines for the process of cross-cultural adaptation of self-report measures. *Spine* 2000;25(24):3186-91.
12. Sousa, V.D., Rojjanasrirat, W. Translation, adaptation, and validation of instruments or measures for use in cross-cultural research: a clear and user-friendly guideline. *J Eval Clin Pract* 2011;17(2):268-74.
13. Herdman, M., Fox-Rushby, J., Badia, X. "Equivalence" and the translation and adaptation of instruments for use in multinational studies of health-related quality of life. *Quality Life Res* 1997;6(3):237-47.
14. Al Amer, H.S., Alanazi, F., ELdesoky, M., Honin, A. Cross-cultural adaptation and psychometric testing of the Arabic version of the Modified Low Back Pain Disability Questionnaire. *PLOS ONE* 2020;15(4), e0231382.
15. Newell, A.M., Van Swearingen, J.M., Hile, E., Brach, J.S. The modified Gait Efficacy Scale: establishing the psychometric properties in older adults. *Phys Ther* 2012;92(2):318-28.
16. Beaton, D.E., Bombardier, C., Guillemin, F. Guidelines for the process of cross-cultural adaptation of self-report measures. *Spine* 2000;25(24):3186-91.
17. Sousa, V.D., Rojjanasrirat, W. Translation, adaptation, and validation of instruments or measures for use in cross-cultural research: a clear and user-friendly guideline. *J Eval Clin Pract* 2011;17(2):268-74.
18. Herdman, M., Fox-Rushby, J., Badia, X. "Equivalence" and the translation and adaptation of instruments for use in multinational studies of health-related quality of life. *Quality Life Res* 1997;6(3):237-47.
19. Özden, F., Özkeskin, M., Şahin, S. Cross-cultural adaptation, reliability and validity of the Turkish version of the modified Gait Efficacy Scale in community-dwelling older adults. *Physiother Theory Pract* 2024;40(1):128-135.
20. Weijer, R.H.A., Hoozemans, M.J.M., van Dieën, J.H., Pijnappels, M. Construct validity and reliability of the modified gait efficacy scale for older adults. *Disabil Rehabil* 2022;44(11):2464-2469.
21. Avelino, P.R., Nascimento, L.R., Menezes, K.K., Alvarenga, M.T.M., Faria Fortini, I., et al. Test-retest reliability and measurement error of the modified gait efficacy scale in individuals with stroke. *Physiother Theory Pract* 2021;38(13):2956-2961.
22. Altmeier, D., Giannouli, E. German translation and psychometric properties of the modified Gait Efficacy Scale (mGES). *Z Gerontol Geriatr* 2020;53(3):251-255.
23. Makizako, H., Shimada, H., Yoshida, D., Anan, Y., Ito, T., Doi, T., et al. Reliability and Validity of the Japanese Version of the Modified Gait Efficacy Scale. *Phys Therp* 2013;40(2):87-95.